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Peer learning and concept tests in physics

G. S. Korpås¹

Department of Physics, Norwegian University of Science and Technology
Trondheim, Norway

M. S. Kahrs

Department of Physics, Norwegian University of Science and Technology
Trondheim, Norway

T. H. Andersen

Department of Physics, Norwegian University of Science and Technology
Trondheim, Norway

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ABSTRACT

The experiences and conceptions about the physical world that students bring into the classroom may support or inhibit them in gaining an understanding congruent with the physical theories. This is relevant for classical mechanics generally, and Newton's laws specifically. Students' preconceptions can therefore represent a threshold for learning.

To address this and get a picture of the students' understanding, they are individually asked to make a drawing of the forces acting on a moving object, provided some initial information. Then, they are given multiple-choice answers based on typical misconceptions. The students choose one of these alternatives by voting with a student-response-system. They also indicate whether they have doubts regarding their answer. After voting, the teacher provides a few comments and gives hints if necessary. The students subsequently discuss the problem in groups, and thereby learn from their peers.

Our results show that even though students indicate few or no doubts regarding their answers to force concept questions, they show signs to hold misconceptions about Newton's laws. Following a group discussion, a second voting in most cases indicates that misinterpretations have been addressed and resolved. In addition to the exercises and the discussion with peers, the students write a short reflection on how the discussion went and how it affected their understanding, in order to utilise the potential of formative assessment.

¹ Corresponding Author
G. S. Korpås
guri.s.korpas@ntnu.no

1 INTRODUCTION

In physics, conceptions from everyday life play a critical role for students' understanding [1]. The experiences and conceptions about the physical world that students bring into the classroom may support or inhibit them in gaining an understanding congruent with the physical theories. This is relevant for classical mechanics generally, and Newton's laws specifically, as Newton's laws are typically applied to situations with which students have extensive experience from everyday life.

In this paper, we present a learning and assessment procedure, in which concept tests are used for identifying and addressing typical misconceptions regarding Newton's laws. Through the students' written reflections, there are indications that this assessment procedure helps to address and resolve their misconceptions.

2 BACKGROUND

Some preconceptions concerning Newton's laws appear to be common among students. One of the most well-known preconceptions implies that in order for an object to maintain a state of motion, there needs to be a force acting on the object in the direction of movement [2]. In an everyday context, this conception makes perfect sense, as friction is ever present. Needless to say, this conception is not congruent with Newton's laws of motion.

In this project, we identified this preconception through a problem (*Fig. 1*) which the students had to solve as part of an in-class mandatory exercise. The problem involved an ice hockey puck which is slid across the ice. The students' task was to identify the forces that were acting on the puck as it slides across the ice, both frictionless and with friction present.

The specific intention with the mandatory exercises is that they should be an incentive towards the students to work evenly on a regular basis. More importantly, the idea is that the students should be able to learn from these exercises, which implies providing the students with information that could further guide them in their learning, i.e., the intention is that these exercises function as formative assessment. Formative assessment, although loosely defined, is an activity characterised by feedback which aims to modify or accelerate learning [3]. Formative assessment can thus be an appropriate way to address students' preconceptions.

A key aspect associated with formative assessment is that the learning activity, and the feedback students receive and provide, should support a mastery goal orientation, which is characterised by students aiming towards learning goals for the sake of learning [4]. In this project, the formative aspect of the mandatory exercises, as well as the feedback that is provided by the teacher, follow the seven principles for good feedback practice developed by Nicol and Macfarlane-Dick [5] (p. 203). Good feedback practice should:

1. Help clarify what good performance is (goals, criteria, expected standards).
2. Facilitate the development of self-assessment (reflection) in learning.

3. Deliver high quality information to students about their learning.
4. Encourage teacher and peer dialogue around learning.
5. Encourage positive motivational beliefs and self-esteem.
6. Provide opportunities to close the gap between current and desired performance.
7. Provide information to teachers that can be used to help shape the teaching.

In order for the teacher to provide accurate and immediate feedback to the students, the students' solutions are gathered by using a student-response-system (SRS). Through the use of SRS, students can also signal whether they have doubts about their solution. Based on the results from the SRS, the teacher decides which problems that need to be addressed, provides the students with some guiding tips, and then instructs them to discuss the problem and possible solutions in small groups. At the end of this discussion, the students are given the chance to give a second response to the problem being discussed. Finally, the teacher makes a summary, providing arguments for both valid and invalid answers. This latter scheme follows the peer instruction method, described by Crouch and Mazur [6].

3 LEARNING ACTIVITIES

To develop the students' understanding of Newtonian mechanics and especially the force concept, lectures and other learning activities address the topic. The learning activities consist of different elements, such as textbook exercises with or without calculations, and practical exercises with a discovery approach.

Once the topic has been thoroughly covered through the structured learning activities, their understanding is addressed through formative assessment. Both discussion and reflection are used as tools, as feedback is a vital part of formative assessment [5]. The aim is that the assessment makes out a learning opportunity, where misconceptions can be addressed and resolved.

3.1 Force concept questions

To address the students' understanding of Newtonian mechanics, they are asked individually to answer the two concept questions shown in *Fig. 1*, where an ice hockey player sends a puck to the right across the ice. The only difference between the two questions is that there is no friction in a), while there is friction in b).

a) An ice hockey player sends a puck to the right across the ice (which has a horizontal surface). First, we assume that there it is no friction between the ice and the puck. Draw a figure, of the puck and all forces acting upon it, after it has been hit.

b) Now assume there are some friction between the puck and the ice. Create a new figure that shows all the forces acting on the puck after the ice hockey player has hit it.

Fig. 1. The two concept questions.

After the students have solved these two concept questions and in addition three calculus-based questions individually, multiple-choice answers are handed out, and the students compare their own answers to the multiple-choice alternatives. The layout of the six alternatives for the two concept questions in focus here, are shown in *Fig. 2*. The alternatives include a various combination of up to four forces acting on the puck, these are the weight (G), the normal force (N), the friction force (R), and a force acting in the direction of movement (F). It is important to include alternative F “None of the previous alternatives are correct” to accommodate other, less known misconceptions among the students.

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1a		None of the previous alternatives are correct				
1b		None of the previous alternatives are correct				

Fig. 2. Multiple-choice answers.

The students answer by using a student-response-system and at the same time signal whether they have doubts regarding their answer. The results of the voting are not revealed to the students at this point. Instead the teacher, based on the results, gives a few comments or even hints if necessary, before the students discuss their solutions in groups. After the discussion, the students are given a second chance to vote. At this point results from both the first and the second round of voting are shown, and it is possible to see how the peer discussion has affected the results.

3.2 Individually written reflection

At the end of the assessment, the students are asked to write an individual reflection. These reflections are handed in as a part of the assignment. According to the seven principles [5] this can help develop self-assessment for the students and it also provides the teacher with information that can be useful shaping further teaching. In the reflection the students comment on how the discussion went and their understanding of the Newtonian mechanics.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Peer discussion increases the number of correct answers

Data is based on assignments from in total 178 students collected from three student groups. The results from the first voting before the discussion and the second voting that is done after the discussion, is compared in *Fig. 3* for both questions.

Fig. 3. Percentage distribution from the first and second voting.

The blue columns to the left present the distribution from the first voting, and the orange columns to the right present the distribution after the discussion and the second voting.

The correct answer to question 1a is alternative B. In Fig. 3 it is seen that more than 40% of the students vote for another alternative. After peer discussion of the problem the second round of voting clearly shows that for most student (91,5%) misinterpretations have been detected and the students choose the correct answer. A similar trend is observed for question 1b, where the obvious answer is D, however alternative F in this case is also considered correct as one may argue that the friction force (R) should be of a smaller value than the normal force (N) and therefore should be drawn with a significantly shorter length as is the case in alternative D.

For both these concept questions the greatest number of misconceptions deals with the preconception of a force acting on the object in the directions of movement, as described by Gilbert and Watts [2]. As the students vote in the first round only 12% and 13% flag to have doubts regarding their answer to questions 1a and 1b, respectively.

For a comparison, up to 60% have doubts about some of the calculus-based questions also included in the test. This is an interesting result, as most of the students who have misinterpreted the Newtonian mechanics are not aware of it.

4.2 Students' written reflections

The written reflections presented here are written by students which have accepted to share them. The focus is on comments that reveal what happens when students learn. When the students are asked to reflect upon potential misconceptions or misunderstandings, this is what they say:

“But after the discussion in the group I realized I was wrong because this was after the puck had been pushed.”

“First, I thought that the questions seemed easy to solve, so when we discussed them in the group and I got several views, I noticed that it is easy to misunderstand the questions. I've learned that I must read the texts more carefully next time, before I start doing the calculations. I also noticed that I misunderstand the use of Newton's laws, today especially Newton's 2nd law.”

This indicates that the questions have worked as intended. Another student emphasises the time to make up one's own mind before engaging in a group discussion:

"I think this was very good! The group discussed, and I think I learned even more because I was able to think and calculate by myself first."

Before the students start discussing they are instructed to let everyone in the group explain their way of thinking. Every student has a contribution to the discussion since everyone has spent time trying to solve the questions by themselves:

"I think the group discussions work very well, everyone in the group contributed and we discussed the procedure, which I find very useful."

"Physics is logical, but sometimes it is difficult to understand "all the logic", but it becomes easier when we work in a group. [...] Furthermore, I want to improve my critical thinking and to trust myself and the answer I think is correct. There were several times I thought correctly, but because I was uncertain, I answered something else."

This last reflection shows when using multiple-choice answers in a formative assessment practice, the possibility of signalling doubt regarding the answer provides important information to the teacher, which should be taken into consideration before the discussion. Several of the students point out that a vital part of the feedback is to see the overall voting result for all the students, which they thereby can relate to their own performance:

"It is also okay to answer using the student-response-system, since you can see that you are not the only one with the wrong answer, as well as seeing the improvement that has occurred from the first to the second voting."

The multiple-choice feature makes it possible for students who does not have a complete understanding of the solution, to contribute to the group discussion. Some students value being able to discuss both valid and invalid solutions:

"Multiple-choice is very nice since you can come up with an answer without understanding all the parts of the task. And it is very easy to discuss afterwards since we can then discuss not only why something is right, but also why something is not right."

"By discussing with the group, one must argue for one's own way of thinking, which means that one reflects more on what one can / cannot do."

Through the reflections from these two students it is obvious that not only the correct alternative has value but also the incorrect ones. By discussing the alternatives, the students learn from their misunderstandings.

5 DISCUSSION AND SUMMARY

Force concept tests in the form of multiple-choice questions are well known in physics education. When looking at the answers alone, one does not see the whole picture. By adding the information about the students having doubts or not, it is possible for the teacher to get a deeper understanding of the students' misconceptions and

immediately give appropriate feedback. Our results show that even though the students indicate few or no doubts regarding their answers, as much as one third to half of the students have serious misinterpretations in the first round. This shows that the students are not aware of their own misconceptions regarding Newtonian mechanics. The discussion and the second voting are therefore important part of the immediate feedback and helps to address the challenges and help them in their learning process.

Using this method, the students receive feedback in several ways; the results of the voting, the explanation given by peers during the discussion and the summary given by the teacher at the end. In addition, the students write a short reflection on how the discussion went and how it affected their understanding. This gives them insight into their own learning experience and promotes learning.

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